

Towards Appreciating Knowing Body in the Future Schools: Developing Methods for School Teachers to Understand the Role of the Body in Teaching and Learning

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Abstract : This paper presents a development project aimed at enhancing student-teachers' awareness of the role of the body in teaching and learning. In this project, theory and practice are brought into dialogue through workshops of body work that utilize art-based and somatic methods. They are carried out in a special course for educating teachers in a Finnish University. Expected results from the project include: 1) the participants become aware of the multiple roles that the body has in educational encounters, and with it, develop a more holistic approach to teaching and learning, 2) the participants gain access to and learn to form bodily knowledge, 3) a working model on enhancing student-teachers' awareness of the role of bodily knowledge in teacher's work is developed. Innovative methods as well as a radical rethinking of the nature of teaching and learning are needed if we are to appreciate knowing body in the future schools.

Keywords : bodily knowledge, the body, somatic methods, teacher education

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